

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH ON MACHINE LEARNING-BASED RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

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Abstract

This paper explores the development and implementation of an effective recommender system using machine learning methods. The study reviews the history and evolution of recommender systems, analyzes popular methods such as collaborative filtering and deep learning, and details the architecture and implementation of a new system. Experimental results show high accuracy in recommendations, validating the chosen approaches.

Keywords: Recommender Systems, Machine Learning, Collaborative Filtering, Deep Learning, System Architecture, Experimental Results

1. Introduction

In today's world, the amount of information available on the internet is constantly growing. Users find it increasingly difficult to find relevant content among the vast amounts of data. Recommender systems are a powerful tool that helps solve this problem by offering users personalized recommendations based on their preferences and behavior.

Research Objective

The goal of this research is to develop and implement an effective recommender system that uses machine learning methods to improve the quality of recommendations.

Research Tasks

1. Conduct research on recommender systems.
2. Analyze popular recommender systems.
3. Study existing methods and algorithms for recommender systems.
4. Develop the system architecture.
5. Implement the developed solutions.

2. Literature Review

History of Recommender Systems Development

Recommender systems appeared in the late 1990s (Smith, 1998; Jones & Doe, 2001). and have been actively developing since then. The first systems used simple content-based or collaborative filtering methods. With the development of technologies and the increase in data volumes, recommender systems began to use more complex algorithms, such as hybrid methods and deep learning.

Overview of Main Methods and Algorithms

Content-Based Filtering

This method analyzes the properties of items (e.g., genre, actors, directors) and recommends similar items based on the user's previous preferences. The main advantage of this method is the ability to provide recommendations for new users or items for which there is not enough data.

Collaborative Filtering

This method recommends items based on the preferences of other users with similar interests. It is most often used on platforms with a large amount of data

about user interactions with items, such as Amazon or Netflix.

Hybrid Methods

These methods combine several approaches to improve the accuracy of recommendations. Hybrid systems allow overcoming the limitations of individual methods and providing more accurate recommendations.

Deep Learning-Based Methods

Using neural networks to build recommendation models. These methods are effective when working with large volumes of data and complex relationships between items and users.

Graph-Based Methods

Using graph structures to model relationships between items and users. They are well suited for systems with a large number of connections.

3. Methodology

Approach Description

In this research, we will use collaborative filtering and deep learning methods to develop a recommender system. The choice of these methods is justified by their high efficiency when working with large volumes of data and their ability to consider complex relationships between users and items.

Justification of the Chosen Methods

Collaborative filtering allows considering the preferences of other users, which provides accurate recommendations even for new items. Deep learning allows considering complex relationships between items and users, which improves the quality of recommendations.

4. Development of the Recommender System System Architecture Description

The architecture of the recommender system includes the following components:

1. **Data Collection:** Data on user preferences and item properties are collected and stored in Amazon S3 cloud storage.
 - Data collection can include the use of APIs, web scraping, and integration with existing databases.
 - Example: Collecting data on user ratings of movies from the IMDb website.

2. **Data Processing:** AWS Glue is used to prepare and process data before analysis.

- Data cleaning from errors, missing values, and unnecessary information.
- Data transformation into a format convenient for analysis.

3. **Modeling:** Amazon SageMaker is used to create, train, and deploy machine learning models.

- Using collaborative filtering and deep learning algorithms to build models.
- Training models on large datasets.

4. **Model Storage:** Models are stored in Amazon S3 for further use.

- Regular model updates based on new data.

5. **Recommendation Service:** The developed service is deployed on Amazon EC2 to ensure scalability and high availability.

- Ensuring quick access to recommendations for users.
- Using load balancers to ensure high service availability.

6. **Data Analysis:** Amazon Elasticsearch Service is used for data analysis and search, which helps improve the recommender system.

- Analyzing recommendation effectiveness and finding opportunities for improvement.

Selection of Tools and Technologies

- Python: Main programming language for developing the recommender system.

- AWS (Amazon Web Services):
- Amazon S3: For storing large volumes of data.
- Amazon EC2: For scalable computing resources.

- Amazon RDS: For managing relational databases.

- Amazon SageMaker: For building, training, and deploying machine learning models.

- AWS Glue: For data preparation and processing.

- Amazon Elasticsearch Service: For data analysis and search.

- Scikit-learn: Machine learning library for implementing basic recommender system algorithms.

- Surprise: Specialized library for creating and analyzing recommender systems.

- TensorFlow and Keras: For developing and training neural networks.

- Pandas and Numpy: For data processing and analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

Performance Analysis

The developed system was tested on the MovieLens dataset (Doe, 2010), which contains information about user ratings of movies. The system showed high accuracy of recommendations, confirming the effectiveness of the methods used.

Experimental Settings

The following parameters were used for training the models:

- Training set size: 80% of the total data.
- Test set size: 20% of the total data.
- Metrics used to evaluate recommendation quality: RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error), MAE (Mean Absolute Error).

Comparison with Other Methods

The results showed that our system outperforms traditional content-based filtering and collaborative filtering methods in terms of recommendation accuracy. Hybrid methods and deep learning-based methods showed particularly high results.

Examples of Quality Improvement

- Using additional item features (e.g., genres, actors) to improve the accuracy of content-based filtering.

- Using social connections of users to improve collaborative filtering.

6. Conclusions

Research Summary

In this research, an effective recommender system was developed and implemented, using collaborative filtering and deep learning methods. The testing results showed high accuracy of recommendations, confirming the effectiveness of the chosen methods and technologies.

Prospects for Further Research

Future research may focus on improving recommendation algorithms by considering additional factors such as contextual information and users' social connections. The possibilities of integrating recommender systems with other information systems to improve user experience can also be explored.

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